

EXPRESSION OF UNITS VERBALIZING THE CONCEPT OF “FEAR” IN ENGLISH AND UZBEKISTAN THROUGH COGNITIVE SLOTS

Akhmadalieva Gulmira Marufjon qizi

*Teacher of Methodology, Department of English Language Teaching, Fergana State
University,*

gulmiraaxmadalievax594@gmail.com

Annotation

This article is devoted to the comparative analysis of lexical, phraseological and paremiological units verbalizing the concept of “fear” in English and Uzbek. The article studies the similarities and differences in the classification of cognitive slots of units in both languages.

Key words: concept, fear, cognitive linguistics, frame, slot, paremiological units.

INTRODUCTION

The study of the notion of “concept”, which is one of the important elements of the field of cognitive linguistics, does not escape the attention of linguists even today. In the field of cognitive linguistics, studying the concept of “Fear” through cognitive slots allows us to classify this concept more broadly. Due to some situations we encounter in everyday life, we fall into a state of fear, and the sequence of processes that cause this state can be shown through slots.

This article aims to analyze the phraseological, lexical and paremiological units expressing the concept of “fear” in Uzbek and English through cognitive slots in the field of cognitive linguistics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The word “concept”, which is the basic concept of the field of cognitive linguistics, has been defined by various scholars to this day, but a clear and stable definition of this term has not yet been given. For example, linguist S. A. Askoldov defines the term concept as a mental formation that replaces an indefinite set of objects of the same type in the process of thinking. According to the linguist Sh. Safarov, “The task of cognitive linguistics is to acquire and store knowledge through language, to apply and transmit language in practice, and in general, to conduct in-depth scientific research into the system and structure of language as a reflection of thought in the human brain.”

At the current stage of the development of cognitive linguistics as a science, its goal is to describe and model the structures of concepts as the basic units of cognitive science. The study of concepts is directly related to the concept of cognitive slots.

A slot represents a chain of various causes that represent knowledge about events. Each frame consists of several slots. The term “slot” was introduced into linguistics, like the term frame, by researchers in artificial intelligence. The concept of a slot can be presented in the form of a sequence of events.

In analyzing the concepts of cognitive slot and frame in the linguistic landscape of the world, the approach of cognitive linguists is an effective way to classify the concept of a concept.

Linguist M. Minsky conducted research on important lexemes in cognitive linguistics, such as frame, slot, script, semantic network. Another linguist, T.A. Van Dijk, also expressed the opinion that “using these terms, cognitive science should form our ability to perform and understand speech acts in its conceptual apparatus, as well as to ensure “influence” on this concept.”

According to the theory of linguist A.P. Chudinov, each frame consists of typical slots, “that is, slots that are considered elements of the situation that include some part of the frame, some aspect of its specification.” A more precise definition of slots can be found in Vasiliev's following remarks: “each sentence represents a concept in a set of conceptual features (quanta of meaning) grouped according to certain aspects (slots)”.

In this article, cognitive slots are distinguished for the concept of fear and their comparative analysis is carried out. We can see lexical units, phraseological units, paremiological units expressing the concept of "Fear" under study.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The lexical units expressing the word "Fear" include such words as fear, afraid, horror, terror, dread, panic, fright, worry, phobia, scare in English.

Phraseological units expressing the concept of "fear" include: *to shake from fear, to quake in one's boots, to be afraid of one's shadow, nearly jump out of your skin, to give someone the willies, to shake like an aspen leaf, to give somebody a start, to give somebody a turn, to get (have) the jitters, to shake in one's boots, To scare someone to death, to scare someone stiff, to frighten somebody out of his life, to frighten someone to death, the heart failed him, to have one's heart in one's shoes, his heart sank, to hold one's breath, to be out of (to lose) one's breath, His face grew white, fear twist one's mouth, his face was destroyed, to go gray, to turn gray, be as white as a sheet, fear runs away with the tongue, to have frog in one's mouth, his tongue was swollen with* includes such as fear.

Paremiological units related to the concept of “fear” may include *shake like a leaf, scared stiff, get/have the jitter, jump out of the skin, break out in a cold sweat, heebie-jeebies, etc.*

Based on the given units, we can compile an analysis table of the concept of “fear” through cognitive slots in Uzbek and English:

Cognitive layer (slot)	English	Uzbek
According to the influence of fear on the human condition	<i>To tremble, to shiver, to shake, to shake from fear, to quake in one’s boots, to be afraid of one’s shadow, nearly jump out of your skin, to give someone the willies, to shake like an aspen leaf, to give somebody a start, to give somebody a turn, to get (have) the jitters, to shake in one’s boots</i>	Qo‘rquvdan dag‘-dag‘ titramoq, qo‘rqqanidan qaltiramoq, a‘zoyi badani qo‘rqqanidan titrab ketdi,
According to the effect on the heart of a person	<i>the heart failed him, to have one’s heart in one’s shoes, his heart sank, To hold one’s breath, to be out of (to lose) one’s breath</i>	Yuragi yorilayozdi, yuragi tovoniga tushub ketdi, yuragi taka-puka bo‘layozdi, yuragi tars yorilay dedi, yuragi shuv etib ketdi.
According to the influence of human speech	Fear runs away with the tongue, to have frog in one’s mouth, his tongue was swollen with fear.	Tili kalimaga kelmay qoldi, tili tanglayiga yopishib qolmoq, tili aylanmay qoldi, tili qotib qoldi.

According to the effect of fear on the human condition *to tremble, to shiver, to shake, to shake from fear, to quake in one’s boots, to be afraid of one’s shadow, nearly jump out of your skin, to give someone the willies, to shake like an aspen leaf, to give somebody a start, to give somebody a turn, to get (have) the jitters, to shake in one’s*

boots, to shake from fear, to tremble from fear, to tremble from body fear, to tremble from body fear,

According to the effect on the heart of a person *the heart failed him, to have one's heart in one's shoes, his heart sank, To hold one's breath, to be out of (to lose) one's breath, the heart was trembling, the heart sank to its heels, the heart was pounding, the heart was trembling, the heart was trembling.*

According to the influence of human speech *fear runs away with the tongue, to have frog in one's mouth, his tongue was swollen with fear, the tongue could not stick to the word, the tongue could not stick to the palate, the tongue could not turn, the tongue was stiff.*

The words “fear” in English and “qo‘rquv” in Uzbek were taken as the main core word of the given phrase, lexical and paremiological units. If we compare some of the lexemes given in the table in the languages under study, the words *boots and shoes* in the phrases *to quake in one's boots and to have one's heart in one's shoes* given in English become somatic lexical in the phrases (*yuragi tovoniga tushdi*) in the Uzbek language.

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that the configuration of concepts such as soul, heart, fear, longing, sadness and others, which are often associated with moral and emotional states, occupies a central place in the study of the field of concepts.

CONCLUSION

It is clear that within the framework of the concept of fear, cognitive slots also differed in the two nations. The difference in the mentality, worldview, thinking and culture of the English and Uzbek people was evident in the cognitive slots of the concept of fear. In this, the similarities and differences of phraseological and paremiological units corresponding to the concept of fear in the English and Uzbek languages, belonging to the peoples of the East and the West, were revealed.